

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE RESEARCH ON THE GENUS *CORTINARIUS* FR. IN THE MYCOBIOTA OF BESSARABIA

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Abstract: The paper presents a synthesis of original data and – from literature on 47 species of the genus *Cortinarius* Fr. revised on the territory Bessarabia. The taxonomic composition of the inventoried species has been determined and analyzed. The key for determining the species of the genus *Cortinarius* was elaborated on the basis of macroscopic and microscopic characters.

Key words: Genus *Cortinarius*, basidiocarp, spore prints, basidia, cystidia, taxonomy, sistematics, Bessarabia

CONTRIBUȚII LA CERCETAREA GENULUI *CORTINARIUS* FR. DIN MICROBIOTA BASARABIEI

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Rezumat: Lucrarea prezintă o sinteză a datelor originale și din literatură privitor la 47 de specii ale genului *Cortinarius* Fr. inventariate pe teritoriul Basarabiei. Se evidențiază și se analizează componența taxonomică a speciilor inventariate. În baza caracterelor macroscopice și microscopice s-a elaborat cheia de determinare a speciilor genului *Cortinarius*.

Cuvinte cheie: Genul *Cortinarius*, basidiom, sporograme, basidii, cistide, taxonomie, sistematică, Basarabia.

INTRODUCTION

Cortinarius Fr. is a genus of lamellar fungi, with ochre, yellow-brown, rusty-brown and dark-brown spores and the sporiferous body with a general and partial veil (cortina). The representatives of this genus have fruiting bodies that are very different in size, colour, density of the flesh and character of the surface of the cap and stem. They can be very small, up to 1 cm tall, and with the same diameter of the cap and very large, up to 10-20 cm. Due to the partial veil and the colour of the spores, the members of the genus *Cortinarius* (common name – webcap) are easily distinguishable. The partial veil, consisting of separate interwoven fibres (like cobweb), covers the lower part of the cap. Rarely, the veil consists of a film, and in species with slimy fruiting bodies, the veil is gelatinous. The veil is kept until the complete maturation of the sporophore, as a fluffy or film ring in the upper part of the stem, and on the edge of the cap, it takes the shape of filamentous rags.

Although the genus is easy to identify in nature, it is very difficult to distinguish between its species, as they have very numerous and sometimes very similar

characteristics. Globally, over 600 species are known [21], in Western Europe – 490 species [13], in Romania – 67 species [19] and in Bessarabia 47 species have been inventoried so far [8, 9, 10].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling of biological material for taxonomic investigation on members of the genus *Cortinarius* has been carried out for more than 4 decades (1976-2019). The methodology of collecting material and processing meets the generally accepted approaches to the study of macromycetes [1, 4, 14]. According to this methodology, macromycetes were collected starting with the appearance of the first mushrooms until late autumn, from various biotopes on the studied territory, in different stages of development. Macroscopic analyses were supplemented with microscopic-photonic ones, which focused on the structure of the hymenium, with special emphasis on the properties of basidia and basidiospores, especially the colour, size, pattern and amyloid reaction of spores. Special attention was paid to biometrics, which has been very useful in determining many species. The identification of taxa was done using the well-known methodology, namely consulting papers that present keys to determine the species [2, 3, 5, 12, 13, 14, 18, 20, 21]. To verify the determinations, some samples of webcaps were analysed in comparison with those from the collections of the herbarium of the Institute of Botany of St. Petersburg. I would like to express my special thanks to Mrs. Ema Nezdoyminogo for her help in identifying difficult species.

It is known that the reference criteria for the characterization of systematic entities are always revised and supplemented; in this paper we were guided by the taxonomic system of the 10th edition of *Dictionary of the Fungi* [7], used by Kirk et al. [22]. The preparation and storage of the samples were also done following the classical methodology [1] with some additions suggested by the author. Dehydrated basidiocarps were placed in a microwave oven to destroy the eggs of insects and then pressed with an iron, packed in polyethylene sachets, which were then placed in paper sachets and labelled. The sachets with the fungal specimens were systematically ordered and inserted in the Herbarium of the “Al. Ciubotaru” National Botanical Garden (Institute) and that of the “Codru” Scientific Reserve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The systematics of the species of the genus *Cortinarius* is complicated and is based on macroscopic and microscopic characteristics. The first attempts to classify this genus systematically were made by E. Fries, who divided the genus *Cortinarius* into 3 series and 6 subgenera [6]. Subsequently, with the detailing of morpho-anatomical criteria and chemical reactions, several classification systems of the genus *Cortinarius* were made [11, 13, 15, 16, 17]. The classification system of the genus *Cortinarius* proposed by Moser (1975a) is the most complex, with well-argued diagnostic criteria, has allowed us to classify the 47 species of webcaps, identified in the study territory, in 6 subgenera, as follows:

Subgenus Phlegmacium (Fr.) Fr. Fleshy basidiocarp. The cap is non-hygrophanous, slimy, sometimes slightly sticky, in some species dry, silky or velvety-felt, of a wide range of colours: whitish, yellow, brown, green, olive, purple or blue-gray. The gills are at first whitish, pale-ochre, blue, purple, yellowish, greenish or olive, but as they age, because of the spores, they become yellow-brown or rusty-brown. The stem is cylindrical, club-shaped or bulbous at the base, dry, silky-fibrous. The veil – from separate fibres on the stem, to very well developed, forming fibrous rings on the stem, and in separate cases, almost film-like rings. Spores are ovoid, ellipsoidal, spindle-shaped, almond-shaped and sometimes globular, from almost smooth to roughly warty. The hyphae of the cap cuticle are 2-8 (10) μm in diameter (*C. amoenolens* Rob. Henry ex P. D. Orton, *C. anfractoides* Rob. Henri & Trescol, *C. arcuatorum* Rob. Henry, *C. balteatocumatilis* Rob. Henry ex P. D. Orton, *C. bergeronii* (Melot) Melot, *C. boudieri* Rob. Henry, *C. caerulescens* (Schaeff.) Fr., *C. caroviolaceus* P. D. Orton, *C. cyaneus* (Bres.) M. M. Moser, *C. dibaphus* Fr., *C. fulmineus* Fr., *C. galeobdolon* Melot, *C. glaucopus* (Schaeff.) Fr., *C. infractus* (Pers.) Fr., *C. largus* Fr.), *C. lividoviolaceus* (Rob. Henry ex M.M. Moser) M.M. Moser, *C. platypus* (M.M. Moser) M.M. Moser, *C. rufo-olivaceus* (Pers.) Fr., *C. sodagnitus* Rob. Henry, *C. splendens* Rob. Henry, *C. olearioides* Rob. Henry, *C. subgracilior* Bidaud & Carteret, *C. talus* Fr., *C. triumphans* Fr., *C. variicolor* (Pers.) Fr., *C. xanthocephalus* P. D. Orton);

Subgenus Telamonia (Fr.) Fr. The cap is hygrophanous, rarely gelatinous, with gills that are transparent at the edge, up to dense-fleshy, smooth or scaly, in shades of different colours of ochre, brown, with or without shades of purple. The stem is from fine and thin to dense and fibrous, with ring-shaped remnants of the veil. The flesh treated with KOH base turns black or brown. The spores are almond-shaped, ovoid, ellipsoidal or globular, from almost smooth to warty. The hyphae of the cap cuticle are 4-20 μm in diameter (*C. brunneofulvus* Fr., *C. bulliardii* (Pers.) Fr., *C. flexipes* (Pers) Fr., *C. hinnuleus* Fr., *C. phaeochrous* J. Favre *C. pseudoprivignus* Rob. Henry *C. suillus* Fr., *C. torvus* (Fr.) Fr. *C. sordescitipes* Bidaud, Moëgne-Locq. & Reumaux, *C. subgracilior* Bidaud & Carteret.);

Subgenus Myxacium (Fr.) Fr. Small or medium-sized basidiocarp. The cap is hygrophanous, slimy or sticky. The stem is slimy or sticky. The veil is slimy. The spores are ellipsoidal, broad-ellipsoidal to globular, almond-shaped and lemon-shaped, from rough to rough-warty. The hyphae of the cap cuticle are 7-20 μm in diameter (*C. barbatus* (Batsch) Melot, *C. elatior* Fr., *C. trivialis* J.E. Lange *C. tabularis* (Fr.) Fr., *C. ochroleucus* (Schaeff.) Fr.;

Subgenus Leprocye Mos. The cap is hygrophanous or non-hygrophanous, dry, felt, felt-scaly, scaly, fibrous, rarely silky. The fruiting body is olive, yellow, red-, orange-, olive-, or ochre-brown. The spores are broad-ellipsoidal to almost globular. The hyphae of the cap cuticle are 6-20 μm in diameter, often with loose-woven ridges. The fruiting body contains a fluorescent substance observed in ultraviolet rays (*C. cotoneus* Fr., *C. melanotus* Kalchbr.);

Subgenus Sericeocybe P.D. Orton. The cap is non-hygrophanous, dry or slightly sticky after rain, smooth or silky and scaly. The fruiting body is blue-violet, clay-yellowish or yellow-brown. The flesh is violet or whitish-blue, when treated with KOH turns brown or brownish-grey. The spores are almond-shaped or broad-ellipsoidal to globular. The hyphae of the cap cuticle are 4-7 μm in diameter (*C. alboviolaceus* (Pers.) Fr., *C. malahchioide* P. D. Orton);

Subgenus Dermocybe (Fr.) Fr. The cap is fleshy-thin, non-hygrophanous, dry, silky or velvety-hairy. The gills are yellow, orange, olive or red. The stem is of the same colours as the young gills. The flesh treated with KOH turns reddish or blackish. The spores are ellipsoidal and seed-shaped, slightly warty. The hyphae of the cap cuticle are 2-8 μm in diameter, without ridges (*C. attenuates* (Velen.) G. Garnier, *C. cinnabarinus* Fr., *C. lacustris* Moenne-Loc. & Reumaux).

In order to identify more easily the taxa of this genus in the field, the key based on macroscopic and organoleptic characters, with some concretizations of the dimensions of the spores, is given below.

Identification of the species

- | | |
|--|-----------------------|
| 1. Slimy cap | 2 |
| – Non-slimy cap | 3 |
| 2. Very slimy stem | 6 |
| – Non-slimy stem | 23 |
| 3. Fruiting body never has violet or blue-lilac hues | 4 |
| – Fruiting body, at least in young specimens, has violet or blue-lilac hues..... | 5 |
| 4. Basidiocarp with other colour variations | 44 |
| – Basidiocarp ochre-brown or brown with a slight olive tinge..... | 9 |
| 5. Hygrophanous fruiting body, the flesh treated with KOH turns black..... | 10 |
| – Non-hygrophanous fruiting body, the flesh treated with KOH does not turn black..... | 22 |
| 6. Basidiocarp with sweet taste..... | 7 |
| – Basidiocarp with bitter taste | 8 |
| 7. Basidiocarp with very gelatinous stem, viscous cap in rainy weather, matte - in dry weather, radially fibrous; spores 10 - 14 x 6 – 8.5 μm in size | <i>C. trivialis</i> |
| – Basidiocarp in rainy weather abundantly gelatinous, in dry weather - glossy, yellow-brown or reddish-brown; spores 10 -15 x 7 - 8 μm in size | <i>C. rickenii</i> |
| 8. The cap of 5-15 cm in diameter, half of it - ribbed, variable color: ocher-brown, gray-purple or purple-brown, lilac-grey then reddish-brown; spores of 13-17 x 7-9 μm | <i>C. elatior</i> |
| – Basidiocarp very bitter, stem only sticky; spores of 7-7.5 x 5-5.5 μm | <i>C. ochroleucus</i> |
| 9. Basidiocarp smelling like radish or raw potatoes; spores of 7.5 -9 x 6 – 7.5 μm ... | <i>C. cotoneus</i> |
| – Basidiocarp without smell like radish or potatoes; spores of 6.5-7.5 x 4 – 5.5 μm | <i>C. melannotus</i> |

- 10. Veil red, red-brown, yellow-brown and brown..... 11
 - Veil white or missing 14
- 11. Veil red or reddish-brown *C. bulliardii*
 - Veil yellow-brown or brown 12
- 12. Stem without rings, bare or with a remnant of silky veil *C. triformis*
 - Stem with one or a few white rings; basidiocarp usually dark brown 13
- 13. Cap on the whole surface with small tufts of hairs, strong *Pelargonium*-like smell *C. flexipes*
 - Cap olive-coloured, on the surface with small tufts of white hairs and with parsley-like smell *C. hemitrichus*
- 14. Fruiting body small, thin-membranous or thin-fleshy 15
 - Fruiting body large, medium or dense-fleshy..... 17
- 15. Fruiting bodies typical for the bottom of dried ponds *C. lacustres*
 - Fruiting bodies occurring in other types of habitats..... 16
- 16. Species typical for areas where willows grow *C. phaeochrous*
 - Species typical for areas where oaks grow *C. pseudoprivignus*
- 17. The fruiting body never has violet hues 18
 - The fruiting body has violet hues at least in young specimens..... 20
- 18. Cap dark brown to ochre brown, gills cream-colored with violet hues, clear pencil-wood-like scent, spores of 9-11 x 7-8 μm *C. brunneofulvus*
 - Cap ochre-brown, reddish-brown to reddish 19
- 19. Cap of 3-5 cm in diameter, with a shallow umbo, strong earthy smell; spores of 7-9 x 5-6 μm *C. hinnuleus*
 - Cap of 3-7 cm in diameter, reddish-brown, silky; gills at first light brown, then reddish-brown; spores of 7-9 x 4-5 μm *C. bivelus*
- 20. Stem bare or with white velum \pm abundant, looking like a cuff; spores of 9-11 x 6-7 μm *C. torvus*
 - Basidiocarp with other characteristics//..... 21
- 21. Species with white or cream stem, radicant and cartilaginous; spores of 9-11 x 6-7 μm *C. subgracilior*
 - Stem not radicant, brownish at the base; spores of 9-11 x 6-7 μm *C. sordescitipes*
- 22. Cap of 5-9 cm in diameter; cuticle fibrous-silky, initially silvery-lilac, in dry weather ochre-brown, stem fibrous, bulbous at the base; spores of 9-11 x 5-6.5 μm *C. malahchioides*
 - Cap of 3-9 cm in diameter, yellowish, with brown tint in the centre; stem cylindrical, thin towards the top; spores of 7.5-9.5 x 5.5-8 μm *C. tabularis*
- 23. Gills in the sporophore are white or pale ochre..... 24
 - Gills of another colour 26
- 24. Cap white, ochre, brown, yellow-brown or orange-brown.....25
 - Cap in young sporophores blue or violet at least on edges 27
- 25. Basidiocarp whitish or grey-violet; stem with one or two membranous rings; spores of 8-9 x 5-7 μm *C. alboviolaceus*

- Basidiocarp pale cream-olive; stem with remnants of brownish silky veil; spores of 11- 13 x 6 - 8 μm *C. triumphans*
- 26.** Flesh of the cap in reaction to KOH does not change the colour or turns slightly brownish **28**
- Flesh of the cap in reaction to KOH turns yellow or at least has a yellow area at the edge **29**
- 27.** Cap covered with ridged fibres, clear fruit-like smell; spores of 8 - 10 x 5 – 6 μm*C. ochropallidus*
- Cap with no ridged fibres, faint, insignificant smell; spores of 10-11 x 6-7 μm *C. caroviolaceus*
- 28.** Cap in young sporophores bluish or violet at least on the edge..... **30**
- Cap in young sporophores yellowish, yellow-brown, greenish or olive..... **37**
- 29.** The base of the stem with marginal bulb **31**
- The base of the stem without marginal bulb **34**
- 30.** Young basidiocarp entirely violet **32**
- Young basidiocarp waxy or grey-bluish..... **33**
- 31.** Cap of 4.5-12 cm in diameter; cuticle radially fibrous, violet-grey or lilac; pores of 9-11 x 5.5-6.5 μm *C. caerulescens*
- Cap of 3-9 cm in diameter, light purple, as it ages, it becomes ochre in the centre and lilac on the edge; spores of 8.5-13 x 5-6 μm *C. sodagnitus*
- 32.** Cap of 5-9 cm in diameter, blue-violet, especially the centre, at maturity the edge becomes violet-brown; spores of 9-11 x 5-6.5 μm *C. cyaneus*
- Cap of 5-9 cm in diameter, lobed margin, viscous cuticle, lilac, pink-violet or cream-purple; spores of 9-11 x 5.5-6.5 μm *C. bouderi*
- 33.** Stem with remnants of membranous veil **35**
- Stem with remnants of silky veil **36**
- 34.** Cap of 5-10 cm in diameter, silky, with pale-violet radial fibres, with a small umbo in the centre, brownish; spores of 7.5-11 x 5-6 μm ...*C. balteatocumatilis*
- Cap of 5-12 cm in diameter, fine velvety, initially lilac-silver, light blue, then brownish-ochre, with radial brown fibres; spores of 9 -11 x 5-6 μm .. *C. largus*
- 35.** Cap of 4-15 cm in diameter, smooth, slightly tomentose, blue or pale-lilac, more ochre towards the centre, with darker radial fibres; spores of 9-12 x 5-7 μm *C. lividoviolaceus*
- Cap of 5-12 cm in diameter, conrescent fibrous, pale purple, then brownish-grey; as it ages, a violet hue is observed only on the edge; spores of 9-12 x 6-7 μm *C. variicolor*
- 36.** Gills, stem and flesh of the cap become dark violet or purple-lilac when pressed**38**
- Gills, stem and flesh of the cap do not change the colour when pressed..... **39**
- 37.** Stem club-shaped; cap initially greenish, then lemon-yellow, with orange hues, then it soon becomes reddish; spores of 10-11 x 5.5-7 μm *C. bergeronii*
- Stem bulbous at the base..... **40**
- 38.** Cap of 7-12 cm in diameter, initially violet and then purple; stem purple, with visible veil remnants; spores of 11-13 x 6.5-7.5 μm *C. rufolivaceus*

- Cap of 7-12 cm in diameter, very viscous in rainy weather, silky and shiny in dry weather, sulphur-yellow, with reddish scales towards the centre, spores of 9-12 x 6-7 μm *C splendens*
- 39.** Flesh of the cap in reaction to KOH turns pink or reddish**41**
- Flesh of the cap in reaction to KOH turns yellow or does not change its colour.....**42**
- 40.** Cap of 4.5-8 cm in diameter, yellow-brown in the centre, with pink-violet hues on the edge; gills blue-lilac, later rusty-brown; spores of 5.5-7 x 10.5-12 μm
..... *C. dibaphus*
- Cap of 4-6 cm in diameter, yellow-brownish, with a violet hue in young specimens; gills pale violet, then rusty; spores of 9-12 x 5.5-7 μm
.....*C. arcuatorum*
- 41.** Cap of 4-9 cm in diameter, ochre or copper, with darker umbo, fibrous, radially wrinkled; gills cream with violet hue; spores of 7-8 x 4-5 μm *C. glaucopus*
- Cap of 5-10 cm in diameter, straw yellow, ochre, sometimes pale olive, initially purple, then terracotta, never rusty; spores of 10-12.5 x 6-7.5 μm
.....*C. amoenolens*
- 42.** Species that grow in spring-summer, negative reaction to guaiac *C. anfractoides*
- Species that grow in autumn, positive reaction to guaiac **43**
- 43.** Cap of 6-10 cm in diameter, bright lemon-yellow, slightly reddish in the centre, gills at first violet, then light brown, spores of 9-11 x 5-6 μm
..... *C. citrinolilacinus*
- Cap of 5-12 cm in diameter, yellow-brown, with shades of green, gills in young specimens with violet hue, then dirty-olive or brown, spores of 6-8.5 x 5-7 μm
..... *C. infractus*
- 44.** Basidiocarp with yellowish hues **45**
- Basidiocarp with reddish hues **46**
- 45.** Cap of 4-10 cm in diameter, lemon-yellow, then brown-orange, with darker scales; gills bright yellow-ochre, then ochre-brown; spores of 8-10 x 5-6 μm
..... *C. olearioides*
- Cap of 5-9 cm in diameter, sticky, reddish-brown, with darker appressed scales all over the surface; gills bright yellow, then brown; spores of 9-11 x 5-6 μm
..... *C. fulmineus*
- 46.** Cap of 3-6 cm in diameter, conical then flattened, with a large umbo, yellowish, cinnabar red to brown; gills cinnabar red, with serrated edge; spores of 7-10 x 4.5-5.5 μm *C. cinnabarinus*
- Cap of 2-5 cm in diameter, campanulate, with prominent umbo, hygrophanous, when wet dark brown, when dry - purplish-brown to dark brown; spores of 7-10 x 5-6 μm *C. anthracinus*

CONCLUSIONS

1. The research on the taxonomic diversity of the genus *Cortinarius* Fr. was completed by identifying 47 species in the mycobiota of the studied territory.

2. The obtained taxonomic data on the 47 identified species made it possible to classify them into 6 subgenera: *Phlegmacium*, *Telamonia*, *Myxacium*, *Leprocycybe*, *Sericeocybe* and *Dermocybe*.
3. The statistical analysis of the number of species within the subgenera revealed the numerical superiority of the subgenus *Phlegmacium*, which includes more than half of the inventoried species (26).
4. The key to identifying *Cortinarius* taxa has been developed, for the most part, based on macroscopic criteria, which will help amateurs to identify webcap species in the field.

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